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UNPATH'D WATERS: People and the Sea

Research Report: Work Package 3.1

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People and the Sea: Work Package 3.1

The work of WP3.1 was aimed at addressing the research aim ‘How can we enhance the significance of submerged and displayed wrecks?’. By using a very wide range of different marine and maritime collections, we wanted to establish the answers to two specific questions:

- How can we establish what engages different people with historic wrecks either onshore in museums or offshore still submerged, and what does that mean for the way we as nations protect and provide access to them?
- How can we enhance the significance of submerged and displayed wrecks and thus increase audience engagement and prioritise management decisions?

The University of Portsmouth (UoP) worked with Partners and Collaborators, Coastal and Intertidal Zone Archaeological Network (CITiZAN), Maritime Archaeology Trust (MAT), Mary Rose Trust (MRT), Nautical Archaeology Society (NAS) and Wessex Archaeology (WA), along with many other consortium colleagues to answer these questions.

The Collections are introduced as exemplars of challenges and opportunities for enhanced digital access to maritime collections. Then the methods, results and analysis of their case studies designed to attract new audiences and promote interest in underwater cultural heritage are described. Finally, recommendations are made to TaNC to improve public access to a future National Collection.

Proof of concept is evidenced through six linked case studies. Mary Rose Museum partnered with UoP Immersive Co-Creation Subgroup to evaluate new animations to improve visitor engagement and explain unanswered questions and misconceptions about the wreck. NAS interrogated dispersed archives to refine Holland submarines information and partnered with UoP Immersive Co-Creation Subgroup to engage new audiences through a hackathon to create a Hollands prototype immersive. MAT created a new Needles Voyager interactive, displayed at public events in the Discovery Bus, to attract new audiences to explore the complex datasets of the Needles wrecks. CITiZAN collaborated with MAT and WP5 in devising value for participants and cross-referencing their citizen-science Solent database with MAT for patterns and shared events. MAT also shared its archive with UoP Analogue Digital Connector which probed beyond digital sources to discover new archival stories about six Needles wrecks, to be added to the Voyager. Analogue Digital Connector also sampled relevant collections for constraints and challenges and asked a symposium of heritage experts to advise on digital policies to achieve a virtual national collection. WA utilised Historic England resources and online databases to explore personal connections to physically inaccessible wrecks through diverse community perspectives.

Common collection challenges for the maritime (and other sectors), but especially maritime archaeology, exist because it has no national framework or funding for curation, conservation, cataloguing and digitisation. Digital access to archives is therefore dispersed and there is no digital national collection for maritime heritage and maritime archaeology.

In all its activities People and the Sea sought to embed Unpath’d Waters’ Values: V1 Equity between people; V2 Connecting with people on their own terms; V3 Collaboration; V4 Reliability & Sustainability; V5 Constructiveness; V6 Adventure.

People and the Sea demonstrates that immense opportunities exist for imaginative interpretation through the senses, scientific research, advanced educational practice and public engagement through a variety of IT tools to make maritime sources available digitally in the future.

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1.2 Summary

The University of Portsmouth worked with Partners and Collaborators, Coastal and Intertidal Zone Archaeological Network (CITiZAN), Maritime Archaeology Trust (MAT), Mary Rose Trust (MRT), Nautical Archaeology Society (NAS) and Wessex Archaeology (WA) to answer these questions. Team members also liaised with other work packages to deliver values, evaluation (WP5), datasets (WP1) and immersive prototypes (WP4).

The Collections are introduced as exemplars of challenges and opportunities for enhanced digital access to maritime collections. Then the methods, results and analysis of their case studies designed to attract new audiences and promote interest in underwater cultural heritage are described. Finally, recommendations are made to TaNC to improve public access to a future national collection.

Proof of concept is evidenced through six linked case studies. Mary Rose Museum partnered with UoP Immersive Co-Creation Subgroup to evaluate new animations to improve visitor engagement and explain unanswered questions and misconceptions about the wreck. NAS interrogated dispersed archives to refine Holland submarines information and partnered with UoP Immersive Co-Creation Subgroup to engage new audiences through a hackathon to create a Hollands prototype immersive. MAT created a new Needles Voyager interactive, displayed at public events in the Discovery Bus, to attract new audiences to explore the complex datasets of the Needles wrecks. CITiZAN collaborated with MAT and WP5 in devising value for participants and cross-referencing their citizen-science Solent database with MAT for patterns and shared events. MAT also shared its archive with UoP Analogue Digital Connector which probed beyond digital sources to discover new archival stories about six Needles wrecks, to be added to the Voyager. Analogue Digital Connector also sampled relevant collections for constraints and challenges and asked a symposium of heritage experts to advise on digital policies to achieve a virtual national collection. WA utilised Historic England resources and online databases to explore personal connections to physically inaccessible wrecks through diverse community perspectives.

Common collection challenges for the maritime (and other sectors), but especially maritime archaeology, exist because it has no national framework or funding for curation, conservation, cataloguing and digitisation. Digital access to archives is therefore dispersed and there is no digital national collection for maritime heritage and maritime archaeology.

Methodologies to attract new audiences to maritime heritage have been devised through a variety of human interactions. In all its activities People and the Sea sought to embed Unpath'd Waters' Values: V1 Equity between people; V2 Connecting with people on their own terms; V3 Collaboration; V4 Reliability & Sustainability; V5 Constructiveness; V6 Adventure.

People and the Sea demonstrates that immense opportunities exist for imaginative interpretation through the senses, scientific research, advanced educational practice and public engagement through a variety of IT tools to make maritime sources available digitally in the future.

1.3 Collections: History, Location, Challenges and Opportunities for Research and Interpretation

Professor Corfield declared, 'All people are living histories – which is why History matters' She continued: 'So understanding the linkages between past and present is absolutely basic for a good understanding of the condition of being human. That, in a nutshell, is why History matters. It is not just 'useful', it is essential.' (Corfield, 2008, Institute of Historical Research).

People and the Sea Research Question: 'How can we enhance the significance of submerged and displayed wrecks?' was distilled as:

- Q1 - How can we establish what engages different people with historic wrecks either onshore in museums or offshore still submerged, and what does that mean for the way we as nations protect and provide access to them?
- Q2 - How can we enhance the significance of submerged and displayed wrecks and thus increase audience engagement and prioritise management decisions?

Shipwrecks might seem a morbid basis for a research project, as they involve disaster, loss and frequently death. But wrecks also signify human creation, productive processes, communication, transference and drama. Ships represent communities of shipbuilders, suppliers of matériel, crew, passengers and cargo, many of these international, and coastal and underwater environments. They can be recovered physically through maritime archaeology, and recreated through art, drama, technology, documents, the senses and emotions. While not everyone can physically visit a shipwreck, People and the Sea has sought to bring the wonder of these phenomena digitally to new audiences to demonstrate the potential wealth of a national collection.

By engaging today's public more widely in past human experiences, People and the Sea case studies have connected and enhanced access to shipwreck collections in the wider Solent area:

- *Mary Rose* displayed wreck and submerged Protected Wreck Site
- *Holland 1 & Holland 5*: displayed museum and submerged protected wreck
- MAT Needles protected and unprotected wrecks: Voyager interactive
- CITiZAN Solent area dataset and nationally linked sites
- UoP Analogue Digital Connector: Collections, 6 Needles wrecks and expert-led Symposium
- UoP Immersive Co-creation Subgroup: MRT/NAS Hackathons, Observations, Holland Prototype

Figure 1, showing the position or area distribution of each of the 3.1 collections. Jasmine Noble-Shelley, MAT.

The physical vessel collections are the most visually accessible. The Mary Rose Museum in Portsmouth Historic Quarter displays *Mary Rose's* partial hull and recovered artefacts (Figure 2), although the protected seabed remains are invisible (Figure 3).

Figure 2. *Mary Rose* viewed from the stern with long galleries beside the ship on three levels containing artefacts positioned opposite where they were found. Both the ship and galleries are within environmentally controlled spaces. ©Stephen Foote

Figure 3. MRT Multibeam image of the site in 2003 with the repositioned hull. The white denotes the original shape of the bow. The timbers from the eroded port side and stem were found in 2003 and 2004. The stem was raised, but the frames were reburied.

Holland 1 is displayed in The National Museum of the Royal Navy (NMRN) Submarine Museum at Gosport, and *Holland 5* is on the seabed, survivors of the first Royal Navy submarine fleet. They offer fewer physical artefacts but connecting them digitally allows comparison and analysis of their experimental mechanisms. All four sites offer immense possibilities of imaginative interpretation through the senses, scientific research, advanced educational practice and public engagement through a variety of IT tools, evidenced here.

Data sources vary. Government archives record the building, career and sinking of *Mary Rose*, but modern accounts document its excavation through 27,560 dives between 1979–82. Its archive, currently being digitised, includes diver's reports, dive management files, archaeologists' journals, underwater photographs and films, remote sensing data, specialist reports, artefact and conservation record cards, archaeological

drawings, site plans, survey data, radiographs, and micrographs. Pre-C20 records include John Deane's 1830s commercial excavations. Each artefact, including the hull, offers insight into life at sea in 1545, each a challenge for curation, conservation, and public engagement. MRT also promotes and develops interest, research and knowledge regarding our underwater cultural heritage.

With *Mary Rose's* recovery in 1982 watched globally by 60 million people, media coverage has been, and still is, vital for funding ongoing conservation, display and storage of the hull and archive. As an independent museum, MRT's overriding challenge is how to re-engage visitors and attract new audiences. Visitors generate most income and merit novel exhibitions, innovative techniques, local outreach, learning opportunities and ongoing research.

The Holland submarines are less celebrated than *Mary Rose*, but Admiralty and contractor archives and newspapers documented this controversially innovative form of warfare, their sinking under tow (*Holland 5*, 1912; *Holland 1*, 1913), and subsequent discovery. Coincidentally, *Holland 1* was recovered a month after *Mary Rose*. Crucially, they represent a unique era of British submarine development and were obsolete before deployment. *Holland 5*, sunk off Sussex, was protected in 2005 under the Protection of Wrecks Act (1973); *Holland 5* Maritime Wreck). It is the only Holland-class submarine on the seabed which can be studied by archaeologists and visited by qualified SCUBA divers.

Exemplifying a particular challenge for maritime archaeology (Ransley and Satchell, 2014), the main research challenge for the Hollands is that their physical and digital archives are widely dispersed. Unpath'd Waters' portal facilitates access to historic environment data, but the aim is to connect them, enabling the public and researchers to interrogate them.

All four sites offer infinite global connective opportunities and experiences through their innovative digital potential.

Complementing these physical collections, Maritime Archaeology Trust (MAT) and Coastal and Intertidal Zone Archaeological Network (CITiZAN) inclusively contextualise and illuminate Solent shipwrecks underwater and in the intertidal zone. The Needles interactive is complemented by resources deriving from consortium members: National Maritime Museum, Lloyds Register, Historic England etc, showing consortium-wide collaborations.

Located at the western tip of the Isle of Wight, the iconic chalk stacks mark the centre of the 150-metre radius of the Protected Needles site, designated under the Protection of Wrecks Act (1973). Prominent are HMS Assurance (1753), a 44-gun 5th rate frigate lost sailing from Jamaica to Portsmouth, and Pomone (1811), a 38-gun 5th rate lost voyaging from the Mediterranean to Portsmouth. Needles wrecks represent 600 years of vessel, aircraft and cultural heritage with regional, national and international connections. MAT links collections to explore underwater archaeology (discovery and recovery), artefacts, ship types, ship losses, shipbuilding, shipyards, ship owners, naval documentation, crews, passengers, life on board, trade, conflict, UK and world ports, cargoes and origins. These data reside in disparate archives, collections and resource centres. While many associated collections are local, regional or national, vessels are essentially international objects, and feature in international collections.

MAT's curation legacy provides public access to archives and databases of archaeological investigations in the Solent through bespoke viewers (one example: Forgotten Wrecks of the First World). This database has enabled new ways to attract more people to explore the Needles maritime archaeology for People and the Sea.

Complementing MAT datasets, CITIZAN trains citizen-science volunteers to identify, record, and monitor England's fragile shoreline archaeology by traditional and digital archaeological recording techniques. It advocates community-led and co-produced data for People and the Sea.

CITIZAN's data focuses on the coast between Mean Low Water and 100m inland of Mean High Water. It highlights coastal erosion threats to foreshore and intertidal sites, the climate crisis impact on coastal communities and the vulnerability of their heritage assets. These encompass a huge time span, many of local or national significance, most lacking statutory protection. Through a smartphone app, over 3,000 registered site surveyors apply a standardised survey and monitoring methodology to all site types, periods and regions. The dataset was based on Historic England's Historic Environment Records (HER) and the National Trust's Sites and Monuments Record. Since 2015 CITIZAN volunteers have identified more than 2,000 new features, updated existing features more than 4,000 times and added 6,000 images. This data is archived with the ADS (Archaeological Data Service), accessible through CITIZAN and Unpath'd Waters portals.

The University of Portsmouth's (UoP) Analogue Digital Connector (ADC) navigated beyond MAT's database, enriching digital data through expert reflection. It created new wreck narratives for the Needles Voyager interactive and identified where online access to digital data ends. It also surveyed sample maritime collections which evidence the diversity of collections relevant to Solent wrecks. These contain records of Portsmouth Dockyard personnel who built and repaired naval ships; historic diving records and artefacts; detailed maps and charts of the Solent unavailable elsewhere; records of British shipbuilding, marine engineering, ship repairing and shipbreaking; and an online database connecting 300,000 dates, 35,000 individuals and 7,000 ships.

UoP's Immersive Co-Creation Subgroup (IC-CS) collaborated with the Nautical Archaeology Society (NAS) and the Mary Rose Trust (MRT) to connect the digital collections of *Mary Rose* and the Hollands interactively through interdisciplinary student engagement. Week-long hackathons combined postgraduate students from Science, Humanities and Cultural Industries to create digital immersive artefacts and innovative interfaces. IC-CS also conducted observations, surveys and focus groups of MRT's new 4D experience about raising *Mary Rose* in 1982.

Also using HER, complemented by many internet sources, Wessex Archaeology's online pilot study tested People and the Sea's engagement objectives. Archaeology on the Seabed – diversifying our engagement with historic shipwrecks explored how important and engaging physically inaccessible wrecks and regional losses can become through diverse community perspectives. It linked disparate archives differently to reflect those audiences' interests. By developing new narratives and a more inclusive understanding of significance, it demonstrated the impact of integrating diversity of interest and voice into any future national collection.

1.4 Case Studies: Methodology, Results and Analysis

MRT and NAS provided high quality raw or enhanced data of *Mary Rose* and *Holland 1* and *Holland 5* wrecks which the UoP IC-CS reshaped and tested through co-creative student hackathons and a Holland prototype immersive. MRT's partnership with the UoP provided extended reality assets, installed in the Museum and evaluated by MRT and UoP IC-CS.

MAT's new Needles Voyager interactive developed interactive ways to engage with a range of maritime archaeological data assets including a diverse range of linked archive and resources. MAT and CITIZAN provided volunteer-enhanced datasets for the UoP Analogue Digital Connector to enrich through new

analogue verified data about six selected Needles wrecks, sample collections and expert feedback. WA's Archaeology on the Seabed linked many internet sources with Historic England's database to engage with ethnically diverse audiences about their interests.

Within Unpath'd Waters, MAT and CITiZAN also worked with WP5 to design participant values and evaluate feedback, IC-CS liaised with WP4 in evaluating interactive experiences. The Analogue Digital Connector collaborated with WP2 in testing digital data accuracy and with WP1 in providing datasets for the Unpath'd Waters portal. The following sections demonstrate how the individual case studies addressed their challenges.

1.4.1 Mary Rose Museum

The Mary Rose Museum evaluated new ways of interpreting its collection to re-engage and attract audiences and correct the misconception that all of *Mary Rose* has been excavated.

The Mary Rose Museum's breadth of research into human and animal DNA, tools, musical and navigation instruments, clothing and weapons was imaginatively refashioned by UoP's Centre for Creative and Immersive Extended Reality (CCIXR). The Enabling XR Enterprise Project (eXRe) explored how extended reality could engage visitors, educate, and entertain through innovative, creative, and immersive technologies. These assets were installed and tested at the Mary Rose Museum, Portsmouth Victorious Festival (65,000 visitors daily) and We Shine Portsmouth Festival of Light in 2022 (2,198 counted visitors).

Holofan

A range of photogrammetry, lidar scanning, 3D modelling software, visual effects software and tools generated a 3D-rendered, looping animation of *Mary Rose* re-forming around the wreck. This blended precise imagery data of the surviving hull, selected artefacts, historical references and archaeological evidence virtually with *Mary Rose*'s structure. The holofan was installed on the museum's upper deck opposite the surviving hull.

Figure 4. Location of the Holofan on the upper decks viewing gallery.

Strips of LED lights on four blades rotated at high speed generated holographic images and videos, creating the illusion of 3D objects floating in mid-air. Visitors experienced the wreck re-forming into the full ship, visual effects showing its sails and flags billowing in the breeze. By recreating the hull's incomplete starboard side from contemporary and modern images, it interprets the incomplete structure. This was very successful, and a larger more permanent installation is being considered. It can also display complete and incomplete scanned artefacts without physically moving or damaging them.

Figure 5. The wreck morphs into the fully rigged ship as the blades spin.

In 2022 evaluation assessed 456 visitor responses to projections into the ship and the Holofan. Feedback was gathered on statements with a 6-point scale of Strongly Agree (SA) to Strongly Disagree with a N/A option or as open-ended comment questions. The 456 total responses were typically overwhelmingly positive. (Complete details available from MRT).

- I learnt something new about the ship or the lives of the people on board from these devices. SA = 56%,
- Using/viewing these devices offered a new insight into the story of the *Mary Rose*. SA = 55.9%
- Using/viewing these devices was a valuable addition to the museum. SA = 57.1%
- It was easy to use/view these devices. SA = 57.5%
- The content of these devices was clear and easily understandable. SA = 56.3%
- These devices were entertaining and enjoyable. SA = 55.9%,

Strongly disagree never exceed 2%.

Leap Motion Experience

This animated underwater journey through the *Mary Rose* wreck on the seabed used 3D models and gaming technologies. It enabled the exploration of the wreck from a first-person perspective, encountering the artefacts and marine life seen by the divers. Installed in the upper deck 'Handling collection', using

interactive leap motion technology, visitors passed their hands over the leap motion sensor to guide themselves through the virtual wreck site. After a 360° wreck exploration, the wreck reformed into the ship.

Figure 6. Installation of the leap motion unit within the museum.

This was not visible to the public, therefore there was no visible ‘draw’, and few visitors found it. Lacking a sign, located in an alcove at the very back of the handling area with the come and try it longbows; if the longbows were in use, you could not even see someone standing at the unit, so there was nothing to attract people. It required manual adjustments morning and evening, and the basic instructions were difficult to follow. However, those who persisted enjoyed the experience, especially because it was self-led rather than pre-determined. However, when it was installed at Victorious Festival and fully staffed it was very effective (Figure 7). If used again, another location would be considered, or a second monitor suitably positioned as an attractor. The lesson learned was that trying to insert new exhibits without reflecting on their role and objectives generates user problems, compared with the holistic approach achievable when the Mary Rose Museum was redesigned in 2013 – a clean slate.

Figure 7. The Holofan unit at the Victorious Festival.

VR Headset Tour 'Our Silent World' (OSW)

This animation created a narrated virtual reality tour of the *Mary Rose*. VR headsets were installed in the Learning Centre in October half term 2022. One was used for specific occasions (i.e the 40th anniversary of the raising). The tour provides a direct connection between the skeleton hull, the displayed objects within the context galleries opposite, and the ship on the seabed during the excavation

Figure 8. Our Silent World - the hull being repopulated with objects during the headset tour.

Audience evaluation of five questions was undertaken between 16 and 20 January 2023, with 60 individuals:

- What did you most enjoy about Our Silent World, and why?
- What did you least enjoy about Our Silent World, and why?
- Have you used VR technology before? If yes, how does Our Silent World compare with your previous experience(s)?
- Was Our Silent World easy to use/navigate? If not, how could we improve the experience?
- Any other comments on your experience today?

14 respondents (23%) cited this as the experience they most enjoyed. They felt they were on a dive, and part of the original diver's experiences was their favourite part of OSW.

The nature of OSW as a virtual reality experience was noted by 11 participants, citing the ability to move their heads, swivel around, and take in the whole environment as the aspect they enjoyed most. 10 participants said that the ability to see the ship from a new perspective was their favourite aspect, and 9 were impressed by the scale of the ship in OSW's final sequence. 6 people noted the graphics and "realism" of OSW as the aspect they enjoyed most.

21 individuals had used VR technology before, 17 rated Our Silent World as on par or above their previous VR experience, whilst one believed OSW to be of a lower quality than their previous experience(s). Further information available from MRT, in Our Silent World, Trial Delivery Report, 2023.

Time Detectives: The Mystery of the *Mary Rose* July 2022

In a pioneering multi-sensory augmented reality game, players became time-travelling detectives tasked with solving the mystery of the *Mary Rose* sinking. It immersed players in the sights, sounds and smells of shipboard life. Using a phone as a 'magical spyglass' to reveal past secrets, players followed a museum trail, based on their chosen 'character'. On their way they collected and interrogated clues to complete their mission for the king¹.

Museum visitors received backpacks which triggered different scents at key moments, for example smelling gunpowder when a gun was fired. To gather information, trigger points activated talking photorealistic 3D characters created from forensic reconstructions of crew members. Primarily aimed at children aged 8–16, this was designed to appeal to a broader, younger and family audience.

This was a challenge. The timetable was too demanding, partly due to meeting set targets for grant-aided funding. Installation required trigger points for activating 'characters' and scents positioned within most museum galleries and needed to be illuminated to work. Difficult to install, this affected existing bespoke lighting for each display case, designed to function together. Tweaking, however minor, affected this balance. Triggers also required players to be in specific positions. This was challenging during busy times, affecting players and other visitors. The long galleries opposite the ship, containing objects with lowered light levels and specific soundscapes, were also compromised. The game affected these already 'immersive galleries'.

There were problems with the company producing the scents. Initial badge-sized activators became large rucksacks with wires from the scent container to the shoulder straps. Having these passed by both MoD (due

¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=L-YiGstQhKg>

to the location of the Museum) and our own Health and Safety standards was 'difficult' and hindered implementation of the complete game. They also required regular refilling and charging, taking extra space and time and imposing extra burdens on staff and volunteers. The game challenged the site internet and did not function with all mobile phones: iPhone and iOS 11.1 or later were recommended. Many of these problems might have been avoided with more detailed explanations and discussions in the planning stage.

Internal Visitor Feedback November 2022–March 2023 confirmed that it worked better at home

- Fun & educational: downloaded this app after a friend recommended it and it's exceeded all expectations...seeing history play out in my living room was surreal!
- Amazing: I found this really educational and interesting adventure. Looking forward to trying it out at the museum!!
- Good idea ... not functioning well: Downloaded at the MR museum to play whilst visiting. App crashed 10+ times throughout. Map showing where to find corresponding clue was on completely wrong level.
- I can't get it to work at the museum. Be careful downloading this at the museum. It wouldn't display the first character properly and there's no way to skip ahead to the next thing to scan, to see if it's just a glitch. I feel I completely wasted my money and the kids are disappointed.

Dive the *Mary Rose* 4D, opened 2023

Connecting the display galleries adjacent to the ship with the seabed excavation, this explained the techniques to excavate, record and raise the ship. It also countered beliefs that nothing of importance remains on the seabed site. This is a permanent experience.

Designed for all audiences in a state-of-the-art 4D theatre, it combines archive assets, CGI and multi-sensory features, including sounds, smells, bubbles, wind and movement. A pre-show relates the ship's sinking in 1545, immediate attempts to lift the ship/recover items of value, the port side erosion, the bow's separation and 20th century rediscovery. Visitors then enter a 40-seater cinema and journey to the wreck site as one of the 500 divers on the excavation. Donning 3D glasses, they plunge into the water and are escorted to the seabed by an original diving archaeologist as the first timbers are discovered. They witness the gradual exposure of the ship and artefacts and see other divers surveying, filming, excavating and recovering objects. They help to raise a gun and tunnel under the ship with a waterjet to secure the lifting wires. Then they witness the lifting of the hull into the cradle and its final lift into the air.

Content was developed by *Mary Rose* diving archaeologists, with members of the original diving, salvage and recovery teams contributing to the creative process and narration. The final sequence fast-forwards to dives in September 2022. It is narrated by the actor Ross Kemp, with a clear message: this is still a Protected Wreck Site, and more is to be found.

Figure 9. Immersing an audience as the *Mary Rose* is raised at the end of Dive 4D.

This has met the challenges and is extremely successful, according to the IC-CS observations and survey (below). However, its success highlights space restrictions within the museum. When busy, cinema queues overflow the seating area and constrain access to other areas, including visitor toilets. When the show finishes, 40 people are queuing from the cinema to the stairs, shop and exit. The last two galleries (at the bottom of the stairs) are largely ignored, possibly due to the successful ‘thrill’ achieved by the experience. More attention should be given to predicting visitor flow and pinch points, based on maximum visitor numbers.

UoP IC-CS/MRT Testing public reactions to the 4D theatre

Mary Rose Observations and Surveys

This explored how immersive experiences are perceived and identified visitors’ current reactions to museum collections/experiences. It would verify what audiences think of immersives, what they want from them, and articulate the social value of the heritage assets. Different audiences (general visitors, academic/researchers and the Bangladeshi community) were tested at different times of the day and different days of the year.

Observations enabled prolonged and immersed access to audience actions and interactions during the immersive experience. This open mode of data collection allowed us to capture spontaneous and unexpected activities/experiences/interactions. The follow up survey captured participants’ immediate

overall impression of impact, cultural value and engagement and emotional responses. The focus group sought to dive deeper into audience reflections and capture more information to contextualise responses.

The team conducted 4 observation and survey sessions:

- General audience 1–7 April 2023: 68 participants (25 observations + 68 surveys)
- Academics/Researchers 8 June 2023: 12 participants (4 observations, 12 surveys + 1 focus group session)
- Bangladeshi Community Group (1): 8 Nov 2023: 14 participants (4 observations + 14 surveys + 1 focus group session)
- Bangladeshi Community Group (2): 2 Feb 2024: 13 participants (2 observations + 13 surveys + 1 focus group session)

Each activity was organised as follows:

- Watch the pre-experience video then join the 4D experience (observations took place during both steps)
- Follow up survey where participants were invited to complete a questionnaire/survey related to their experience
- Follow on focus group where the survey areas were contextualised and explored in depth with participants

It was not possible to run interviews/focus groups with general audiences, so this activity was run only with academics and two Bangladeshi community groups.

General Audience Feedback: Global Quality of Experience

In the post-4D experience survey, participants rated the *Mary Rose* 4D Experience using five global experiential quality dimensions on a scale of 1-5, with higher scores indicating a more positive perspective (e.g., Good vs. Not Good, Powerful vs. Not Powerful). The *Mary Rose* 4D Experience is generally well-received, with high ratings across all quality dimensions, particularly for its uniqueness and storytelling aspects.

Overall Reception: Rated highly across experience quality dimensions

Memorability: High ratings indicated that most found it a memorable experience.

Figure 10. Overall rating of the MRT 4D experience quality and resonance.

The data indicate that the experience successfully provides a positive, novel, and engaging activity for its participants. Most participants rated the experience as 5, with an average rating of approximately 4.78, indicating very high overall satisfaction. The 4D experience is generally perceived as powerful, with a significant majority giving it the highest rating. However, there is a slight variation in responses, suggesting areas for potential enhancement to ensure a consistently powerful impact for all visitors. Regarding memorability, most participants gave high ratings, indicating that respondents mainly found the experience memorable.

Participants were then asked to rate their experiences using two specific statements: "The *Mary Rose* 4D experience was different from things I've experienced before" and "The *Mary Rose* 4D experience allowed me to explore new stories." Ratings were collected on a Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). The survey results suggest that the *Mary Rose* 4D experience is perceived as highly unique and engaging by most of the general audience participants. A significant majority of respondents rated the experience as either "Strongly Agree" or "Agree" for both evaluated statements. Specifically, 50 participants (87%) agreed or strongly agreed that the experience was different from what they had encountered before, while 50 participants (87%) also agreed or strongly agreed that the experience allowed them to explore new stories. Notably, there was minimal disagreement, with only two participants (3%) disagreeing that the experience was unique and one participant (1%) disagreeing about the exploration of new stories. This low level of disagreement underscores the overall positive reception.

Cultural Value Feedback

Alongside the global experiential quality ratings, the survey also used questions related to the perceived cultural value of the content. Firstly, participants were asked to rate if the 4D experience was an interesting idea. Most respondents rated the *Mary Rose* 4D Experience very positively. Scores of 4 and 5 dominate the responses, indicating that most people found the experience to be interesting or very interesting. 75 respondents rated the experience as a 5, indicating that they found it very interesting. On average, participants viewed the *Mary Rose* 4D Experience favourably in terms of whether they would want to experience it again, reflecting a strong inclination towards it being an enjoyable activity. A significant majority of participants rated it as a 5 (42 out of 63 responses), indicating a widespread desire to repeat the experience.

Participants were also asked to rate their agreement or disagreement with statements regarding the personal relevance, comfort level, intellectual challenge, and introduction of new ideas during the experience. Participants overwhelmingly felt that the *Mary Rose* 4D experience was personally relevant, with 68% indicating agreement (Agree or Strongly Agree) with the statement "I felt like the *Mary Rose* 4D experience was made for me." In terms of comfort, responses were varied: 42% agreed or strongly agreed that the experience sometimes made them feel uncomfortable, while 31% were neutral, and 27% disagreed or strongly disagreed with this statement.

In terms of intellectual challenge and provocation, a substantial majority (73%) agreed or strongly agreed that they felt challenged and provoked during the experience. The positive reception and perceived intellectual stimulation suggest the effectiveness of the experience in engaging participants and broadening their perspectives. Similarly, most participants (70%) agreed or strongly agreed that the *Mary Rose* 4D experience opened their eyes to new ideas.

IC-CS *Mary Rose* Hackathon 2022 to test the methodology

NAS also provided data for a Hollands Hackathon immersive to improve public engagement.

NAS and UoP IC-CS ran a competitive Hackathon (23–27 October 2023) for 15 students from science, humanities, business, art, creative and digital practices to work in teams. They were tasked to co-design an interactive innovative interface to link and improve access to scattered Holland archival materials. They also explored what engages different people about data and heritage aspects of museum and submerged historic wrecks, and implications for the way nations protect and provide access to them.

Project partners and students formed a co-creation ‘community of researchers’ who welcomed immersion within one problem in depth for a week. Exploring a topic intensively was considered more effective than many short meetings over a long period. This Hackathon verified methods of engaging multi-disciplinary students in finding solutions to communicate and engage audiences in unfamiliar heritage data (historic DNA).

The brief was to design and build an interactive innovative interface communicating scientific and heritage data. This was mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) extracted from bones excavated from *Mary Rose* and sequenced. As genetic information passes directly from mother to child with little significant change, it can trace ancestry across multiple generations. The challenge was to take potentially intimidating mtDNA sequence data and present it invitingly to a non-specialist (Figures 11 and 12 Presentations, University of Portsmouth and Mary Rose Trust Hackathon 2023).

Figure 11. Mary Rose Hackathon Presentation – The Storytelling Gamified Concept

Figure 12. Mary Rose Hackathon Presentation – The coding and geographic navigation concept

Team 1 targeted researchers and built a data navigation method using a coding system and lib motion capture controller for an immersive experience and engagement with the data.

Team 2 targeted children and built a gamified and interactive illustrated experience to engage the younger generation/children with the data through interactive narratives. It used its visual media and illustration strengths to build the interactive narrative and story².

Team skills and target audiences strongly influenced how the experience was synthesised and articulated visually and interactively. One aspect stands out: the negotiation of crossing disciplinary boundaries can inspire new ideas, insights and conversation. How the community of researchers established a routine and common language, evolved prototypes, and overcome obstacles was instructive.

Participants were challenged by collaboration crossing disciplinary boundaries:

- How can I communicate, what I need and what I want?
- How can I explain datasets, digital tools, creative practice and approaches to researchers and practitioners from other disciplines?

² YouTube <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=u-XB7R19LYQ> The Royal Archer

Outcomes highlight how the effort to cross disciplinary boundaries is rewarding. It can generate a wide range of valuable ideas and innovations not produced within traditional disciplinary silos. The diversity of group membership created a diversity of creative innovation which yielded many insights and explored directions not previously considered by the owners of the maritime heritage data.

Building varied and balanced expertise teams was key. Speed-dating techniques allowed participants to test each other's skills, interests and topic connections before selecting teams to respond to the challenge and co-create prototypes, demonstrating that social aspects are part of co-creation.

Other lessons:

- Setting achievable targets within the timeframe is critical to achieve the best co-creation results
- Defining a space to connect people is key to enabling meaningful collaboration and outcomes.

One output, "Submerged Heritage", connected archives through a navigation strategy using the concept of SCUBA diving as a metaphor and storytelling as a vehicle (Figure 13). The second output used a gaming interface to enable audiences to interact with archival materials.

Figure 13. The Submerged Heritage explorer concept © University of Portsmouth.

This team created an interactive and intuitive digital platform which could be adapted for different audiences. They aimed to build an application in a 'discover' or a 'directed' format with detailed information for academic researchers which would also engage the public with this interesting period of maritime history.

1.4.2 *Holland 1 and Holland 5*

The Nautical Archaeology Society sought verifiable data in dispersed Holland archives to correct errors and improve public engagement. Systematic archive searches revealed hidden data and data gaps:

Nautical Archaeology Society (NAS)

NAS has visited and documented the *Holland 5* wreck since 2010, initially through its Education Programme where students studied an early submarine class on the seabed. A virtual diver trail allows online exploration of the wreck³ (Figure 14). This was one of the first developed for underwater historic assets and included a tour of the wreck and the Holland class history. It links the National Heritage List for England entry but did not provide access to the archives.

Figure 14. The virtual dive trail of the Holland No.5 submarine developed by the NAS and 3Deep Media © NAS

NAS's condition assessment of *Holland 5* (NAS 2014) evaluated the Archaeology Diving Unit (ADU) 2000 and 2001 geophysical surveys (ADU 2001), and Wessex Archaeology investigations (Wessex Archaeology 2006b, 2007, 2008, 2008b, 2012).

³ <https://www.nauticalarchaeologysociety.org/holland5-dive-trail>

Gerry Dowd, finder of *Holland 5*, holds his own archive and was interviewed about the discovery, as was the current protected wreck licensee, Sara Hasan. These recordings are archived by NAS. The NAS digital and analogue archive held at Fort Cumberland, Portsmouth and on cloud servers has been made available to Unpath'd Waters.

The National Archives (TNA)

This documents the geopolitical context for developing the submarine fleet, the loss and salvage of *Holland 1* and the loss of *Holland 5* in ADM 12 (Admiralty) and DEFE (Defence). ADM 12/1498 shows *Holland 5* 'broken adrift from Tug' on 8 August 1912 and a 'search in [the] channel'. ADM 12 is not accessible online, so researchers must visit TNA to discover documents. "Holland" in ADM 12 in the online catalogue returns zero results, so researchers would therefore assume nothing on the first submarine fleet is contained in ADM 12.

Historic England / Heritage Gateway

A search on Heritage Gateway "Holland Submarines" reveals Hob Uid⁴: 1397999 for *Holland 5*'s wreck site discovery and early work but omits post-2010 licensed divers' visits or surveys for the Protection of Wrecks Act. It states: 'Several photographs of *Holland 5* are available on the Wrecksite.eu website (February 2023).' NAS's 2014 condition assessment for Historic England is also missing (NAS, 2014).

The *Holland 5* entry on Historic England's National Heritage List for England⁵ includes basic history and discovery, some duplicated in Heritage Gateway. Comments and photographs include contributions by the NAS, Historic England and contractors, including a hyperlink to the NAS 2014 condition assessment.

Cumbria Archive Service

Cumbria County Council Archives hold 4 images of Holland submarines, built in Barrow-In-Furness, available digitally on request. Vickers-Maxim boatyard archives, now operated by BAE Systems, are held by the NMRN.

National Museum of the Royal Navy (NMRN)

NMRN curates and displays *Holland 1* at the Submarine Museum in Gosport with the first submarine fleet items and documents (Figure 15). While the Unpath'd Waters project was active, NMRN improved online access to their archives, so researchers can search the online catalogue of 121 documents⁶, 47 technical drawings, 8 photographs, 5 fittings, and 1 silver snuff box (Object Number RNSM G02/2/82). Engraved on its lid is a small anchor and 'Thos O' Halloran Coxn. No 4 Submarine Sept 1903'.

⁴ HE Accessioning Guidance: Historical Object Unique Identifier - <https://nrhe-to-her.esdm.co.uk/accessioning-guidance>

⁵ <https://historicengland.org.uk/listing/the-list/list-entry/1000081?section=official-list-entry>

⁶ <https://www.nmrn.org.uk/collections>

Figure 15. The Holland No.1 submarine on display at the Royal Navy Submarine Museum © NAS

In 2023 NMRN created a tile on their archives webpage, making the Holland collection more accessible. In 2024 digitisation of the Holland archive is incomplete but facilitates access to the Royal Navy's first submarine fleet (Figure 16).

Figure 16. Examining engineering plans of the Holland class of submarines held by the National Museum of the Royal Navy © NAS

University of Cambridge Library online ArchiveSearch

This reveals several images of the Holland submarines from the Vickers-Maxim archives and Admiralty contracts with Vickers-Maxim to build the five Holland boats.

UK Hydrographic Office Taunton (UKHO)

Holland 5's loss under tow from Portsmouth to Sheerness is described in a letter from HMS Harrier at Portsmouth, 10 August 1912 (HD667-1912). Harrier assists the tug Enterprise in searching for the 'derelict submarine'. 'Torpedo Boat No.2' was also directed by Beachy Head to join the ultimately unsuccessful search in the Channel. UKHO will supply a digital scan for a small fee.

Archaeology Data Service (ADS) ArchSearch

"Holland submarines" returns two records: Ultrasonic thickness measurements of the Holland No.5 and the HMS m/A1 submarine (Wessex Archaeology 2012) and 2006 Designated Site Assessment (Wessex Archaeology 2006). "Submarine" returns HMS/M A1 condition survey (Wessex Archaeology 2006b, <https://doi.org/10.5284/1017435>).

OASIS

OASIS is the online system for reporting events (i.e. investigations) relating to the historic environment and linking research outputs and archives⁷

"Holland submarines" returned no results.

Other archives identified by UoP researcher Daisy Turnbull

The Wellcome Collection holds *The Navy and Army Illustrated*: 5 April 1902 issue covering the first Royal Navy submarine's launch and trials (Figure 17).

⁷ <https://oasis.ac.uk/>

Figure 17. Our First Submarine! The Navy and Army Illustrated, April 5th 1902. © Licence: Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International (CC BY-NC 4.0). Credit: Navy and Army Illustrated. Source: Wellcome Collection.

Royal Museums Group Greenwich displays a hull model (SLR0111) in the Sea Things Gallery and depictions of the Holland class submarines, including a drawing of a Holland-type submarine in Portsmouth Dock No. 6.

Hansard UK Parliamentary Archives hold material on Holland submarines and decisions to focus effort and resources on developing submarines:

- 13 March 1899: Navy Estimates: ‘without reserve the decision of the Minister of Marine to suspend for 1899 the ordering of a new battleship, so as to concentrate all available resources on cruisers, torpedo boats, and submarine vessels.’
- 17 July 1900: Navy Estimates (debate on the merits of submarines): There have appeared in our papers pictures of the Holland boat. It is not an experiment even in its early stages; it is worked out to the most minute nicety. You have an arrangement of electric motor power for travelling under the water; of gas power for searching; you get a speed of eight knots under the Toggle showing location of water, and of fifteen knots on the surface. I saw it stated that the United States are to add fifty of those vessels to their fleet’.

British Newspaper Archive: Verifying online data

Available by subscription, this digital resource includes numerous entries for new interesting stories of the development, ordering, building, testing, service history and loss of the Holland submarines.

Evidently the press was fascinated by the Royal Navy’s first submarine fleet. The Leicester Evening Mail (10/08/24) and the Hull Daily Mail (12/8/12) even detailed *Holland 5*’s successful salvage, despite its existence on the seabed. The Weekly Dispatch (London) stated that the submarine was ‘taken round to Sheerness’ (11/08/12). Further research would be worthwhile to explore the reasons why.

Countering previous understanding, Daisy Turnbull found evidence that the Hollands’ inventor John Philip Holland visited England in 1899 to meet the Admiralty to secure the contract for the five boats of the first submarine fleet:

17 March 1899 Derby Daily Telegraph (Washington, USA): “Alleged offer by the British Government”. “Mr J.P.Holland, the inventor of the Holland submarine torpedo boat, has gone to London to sell his boat to the British Government. With Mr Holland went Captain D.K Bell, R.N., who has spent some months in this country (The USA) investigating the merits of the boat”. It continued, “Mr Holland’s partner says the success of the French submarine boat, stimulated the British Government to make an offer for the Holland boat. Mr Holland offered during the Spanish war to go into Santiago harbour at his own risk and expense and blow up Cervera’s fleet. The Government refused the offer.”

9 May 1899 Scarborough Evening News published the 8 May New York report: “Submarine Ignorance”. “U.S. Inventor says we shall be rudely enlightened.” It states that “Mr John Holland, the inventor of the submarine boat, returned from England on Saturday. He has denied the report that he went abroad to try to sell the boat to the British Government. Mr Holland while visiting London met with a number of leading English marine engineers and was astonished by their ignorance of submarine boats, although they were ready to condemn them.”

Holland Digital Survey

To enrich audience experiences of *Holland 1* and *Holland 5*, NAS created new digital data to enable UoP IC-CS to test audience engagement through an immersive viewer

In July 2022 NAS and Martin Davies of InDepth Photography carried out a new photogrammetry survey of the *Holland 5* wreck site (Figure 18) for a new digital dataset to develop an immersive viewer with UoP.

In September 2022 Centre of Maritime Archaeology staff at the University of Southampton took a laser scan of the exterior and the interior of *Holland 1* for the immersive viewer (Figure 19). *Holland 1* had never been

laser scanned before, so the dataset is a valuable new Unpath'd Waters resource donated to NMRN for its management, display and interpretation.

Figure 18. Photogrammetry model of the Holland No.5 submarine carried out in 2022 by InDepth Photography for the Nautical Archaeology Society © InDepth Photography.

Figure 19. 2022 Laser scan of the Holland No.1 submarine carried out by the Centre for Maritime Archaeology, University of Southampton © CMA, University of Southampton.

Holland Hackathon

NAS and UoP IC-CS ran a competitive Hackathon (23–27 October 2023) for 15 students from science, humanities, business, art, creative and digital practices to work in teams. They were tasked to co-design an interactive innovative interface to link and improve access to scattered Holland archival materials. They also explored what engages different people about data and heritage aspects of museum and submerged historic wrecks, and implications for the way nations protect and provide access to them.

Employing storytelling, immersion, searchable, adaptable and expandable concepts, “Submerged Heritage” was deemed worthy of amplification by the project team after the Hackathon.⁸ In February 2024 a second phase developed this concept into a working digital interactive prototype in collaboration with NAS and NMRN Submarine Museum in Gosport. Three UoP early career researchers, including two from the original Hackathon team, produced the first prototype at the end of March 2024 (Figure 20).

Figure 20. Screen grab of the Holland Submarine Fleet Explorer (Prototype) © University of Portsmouth.

⁸ Inspired by D. Polydorou, Immersive storytelling experiences: a design methodology, 2024, <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/14626268.2024.2389886>; A. G. Privitera, F. Fontana & M. Geronazzo, The Role of Audio in Immersive Storytelling: a Systematic Review in Cultural Heritage, 2024, <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11042-024-19288-4>; J. Cummings, M. Tsay-Vogel, T. J. Cahill & L. Zhang, Effects of immersive storytelling on affective, cognitive, and associative empathy: The mediating role of presence, 2022, <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/1461444820986816>

Figure 21. Screen grab of the Mr Holland page on the Holland Submarine Fleet Explorer (Prototype) © University of Portsmouth.

The new visualisation interactive, called the Holland Submarine Fleet Explorer (Prototype), with the generous support of NMRN staff, was tested on Submarine Museum visitors and school children during April 2024, to collect their feedback (Figure 22).

Figure 22. The University of Portsmouth team hosting a Holland Submarine Explorer (Prototype) testing session at the Royal Navy Submarine Museum © NAS

Key findings about how visitors engage with submarine history and heritage and what they wish to discover about early submarines:

- Few visitors were aware before their visit that the museum curates and displays a Holland class submarine or of early Royal Navy submarine development and the role of an Irishman, John Philip Holland. None knew that *Holland 5* exists or that Holland 2, 3 and 4 were in the first Royal Navy submarine fleet.
- Visitors found experiencing the Holland Explorer (Prototype) informative and interesting because they could dive into areas or themes through their own interests and navigate directly to certain stories. They engaged most positively with the Explorer's visual media: video clips and photos embedded into the prototype.
- Explorer users emphasised that text should be kept simple and short, focused on the most important information.
- Feedback demonstrated that visitors liked learning more about people, including John Holland, Captain Bacon and the brave first crews of the Royal Navy submarine fleet. They wanted more access to visual information, especially videos.
- Visitor key learnings: awareness of the existence of the five submarines, *Holland 5* under water, how they were found, the raising of *Holland 1* and its journey to Gosport, including being cut up for transportation, and appreciation of the time needed to raise the submarine.
- School children engaged well with the experience and the text. As the Explorer was not specifically designed for children, this countered research team expectations. Some children asked for more visuals but many spent time reading and discussing what they learnt from the experience

1.4.3 Maritime Archaeology Trust Needles Voyager

Maritime Archaeology Trust designed the Needles Voyager interactive to provide new ways for audiences to explore Needles maritime archaeology. Voyager digitally connects collections relevant to the Needles Protected Wrecks, nearby non-protected wrecks, crashed aircraft and maritime shoreside features (Figure 23). Visitors can explore an interactive map geographically to discover maritime archaeological stories. These are based on sources (reports, photos, audio, video, 3D models, linked sites) or themes such as individual ships, artefacts, ship types, shipbuilders/yards, ship owners, documentation, crews, passengers, ports or cargo.

Voyager uses MAT's in-house PostgreSQL database with PostGIS spatial extensions (open-source software). It employs a web interface in HTML, using JavaScript, CSS and PHP. Due to the density of wreck sites, the project focuses on a 2.5-kilometre radius from the Needles. Building on previous projects, and wreck sites exhibited in the Isle of Wight Shipwreck Centre and Maritime Museum (SWC), MAT has undertaken research enhancement using available online sources, cross-checked with Historic England's Historic Environment Records (HER) data via Heritage Gateway. This process identified HER updates with more precise positions, one site being moved substantially from the area. This demonstrates the potential for detailed local databases and use of online digital archive sources, such as The British Newspaper Archive, to enhance the national record.

Development benefited from a simultaneous project where volunteers digitised MAT archive material and developed new digital, significantly enhanced outputs (Fathoming the Future). Content was enriched by audio articles, site summaries, digitised historic reports and a Needles wreck-inspired poem in text and audio form. Local contributions include an extensive collection of artefact photographs from the Needles excavations from the Isle of Wight Museum Service and historic photographs and postcards of the former Alum Bay Pier from the Carisbrook Castle archive. This demonstrates potential for linking local archive sources.

MAT's database benefited from a new 'archives links' table which includes data from the Unpath'd Waters collections sample. Clicking on these links opens a new Voyager window to online content without leaving the application and connects Needles sites to related online archive material:

- HER data through Heritage Gateway
- TNA entries
- Lloyds Register Foundation documents – plans and surveys
- Royal Museums Greenwich - photos and archive
- ADS Unpath'd Waters Portal entries
- CITIZAN entries
- Wrecksite.eu entries
- Crew List Index Project
- Specialist websites for different vessel types such as Naval-history.net, NavSource, U-boat.net, Tyne Built Ships, RNLi archives.

The Voyager is available online: <https://unpath.maritimearchaeologytrust.org/>

Figure 23. The Needles Voyager showing the stern section of the *Serrana* wreck selected with an underwater diver image being viewed (MAT)

CITiZAN and Needles Voyager

Once the maritime and coastal features featuring in the Needles Voyager were established, they were cross-referenced with CITiZAN's dataset to check unique events. CITiZAN's dataset was interrogated for sites which might have a historical or thematic link to the Voyager features. A pair of parameters were set for the subsequent data subset; all sites within the subset requiring a narrative link to the subject feature or sharing the same 'site type'. For example, sites with a narrative link to *Campen* (Dutch East India Company vessel) included *Vliegende Draeck* (CITiZAN Id: 58462) which accompanied *Campen* and was fatally damaged on the same passage and subsequently beached at Yarmouth. *Moon* (CITiZAN Id: 59668), a vessel which belonged to the English East India Company, was stranded off Dover Castle and salvaged by the diver Jacob Johnson, who also dived on *Campen*. Sites with the same 'site type' of the subject feature had to be constructed within 10 years of the subject. For example: the Godrevy Lighthouse (CITiZAN Id: 83598 – site type: Lighthouse), located off the north Cornish coast, was opened in the same year as the Needles Lighthouse and was designed by the same architect, James Walker.

Linking Needles Voyager features to the broader CITiZAN dataset increases the narrative depth of Voyager and gives the public a broader understanding of the subject feature. The citizen-science nature of CITiZAN methodology, combined with the project archive, enables the archaeological record of Voyager's study area to be enhanced by Voyager users without much difficulty. The inclusion of the CITiZAN dataset within Voyager has also increased viewers to CITiZAN's website and dataset. The user response to the CITiZAN record for the Needles Lighthouse, had a 200% increase in page viewers for the period the Needles Voyager was active (October 2023 – August 2024), above the preceding 11 months. The archaeological record for the feature was also updated with more recent photographs during Voyager's monitored period. This was a resounding vindication of public engagement with Voyager.

Analogue Archives and Needles Voyager

MAT's Needles/Solent/Channel wreck datasets were enriched from physical archives to enhance the Needles Voyager interactive by curating new shipwreck stories. This identifies where online access to digital data ends and where analogue archives have the potential to enrich identities of place and people.

Selected archives/collections were surveyed to identify exemplar digital status and public accessibility to find silent knowledge and unite different collection types more effectively.

To demonstrate that expert researchers can find new analogue material on six selected Needles wreck vessels which were locally built or habitual visitors to the Solent/Channel, new narratives were researched to engage Needles Voyager audiences.

Selection criteria for Needles wrecks

- Located within a 2.5km radius of the Needles wreck site
- History appealing to audiences
- Prior Solent/Channel relationship (built/habitual visitor)
- Scarce related digital/analogue data available
- Representative vessel classification (RN/commercial/type/size)
- Representative date range

Selected Needles vessels wreck dates

- *Campen/Kampen*: 1627 Dutch East India (Vereenigde Oostindische Compagnie, VOC) yacht or pinnace
- HMS *Looe*: 1705 5th Rate frigate
- HMS *Incendiary*: 1780 fire ship
- *Queen Charlotte*: 1815 troop ship
- SS *Serrana*: 1918 cargo and passenger ship
- *Anglo Saxon*: 1879 Channel Island brig

Based on MAT and HER, online catalogues of the main repositories (TNA, British Library: BL and the National Maritime Museum: NMM) were searched. BL's Archives and Manuscripts catalogue was searched for "The Needles" yielding 55 records, mostly photographs. "Isle of Wight" gave 737 records in Western Manuscripts; 470 of which were reviewed for 18th- and 19th-century manuscripts, mostly tour journals containing sketches and charts. "Shipwrecks", "ship wrecks", "wrecks", "disasters, sea" yielded zero returns. "The Needles" were invisible as a maritime location but appeared within terrestrial accounts⁹. The information varied in results, with Royal Navy vessels the richest, then the WW1 torpedoed cargo ship, and most difficult the hired troop ship and the small Guernsey brig.

Kampen/Campen 1627 Dutch East India (Vereenigde Oostindische Compagnie, VOC) yacht or pinnace

Kampen was part of a VOC fleet to the East Indies, a three-masted 300-ton wooden yacht or pinnace, newly built in VOC Amsterdam, carrying a cargo of silver coins and lead ingots, 160 soldiers, passengers and crew, which ran aground on 13 Oct 1627 OS¹⁰ after 'threading the Needles' (sailing through the largest gap in the rocks).

Larn, 1985, parts 1 and 2, and HER were useful secondary sources for detailing the wreck, the Amboyna context, the Dutch town of Kampen and transcribed some Calendar of State Papers Domestic (CSPD) and Venetian entries. *Kampen* is absent from TNA Admiralty records, but State Papers (SP 84) detail the 1623 Amboyna incident and subsequent Anglo-Dutch friction in the Solent. High Court of Admiralty (HCA) sources record Anglo-Dutch negotiations and the diver's recoveries¹¹. The Rijksmuseum catalogue has no results for "VOC *Kampen*" but provides free downloadable images of *Kampen* in Overijssel Province which minted silver coins 1371–1796 (Rijksmuseum, Paulus van Wtewael).¹² Thus, Privy Council records in CSPD and Venetian were the main sources. Library copies were required as online versions sit behind a paywall¹³.

⁹ For example, BL, Add. MS 73492, fol. 28, The Needles before Lot's Wife Fell in 1764, although it is dated 1765; Add. MS 33650, sketches of the Needles 1817, fols 96-10.

¹⁰ The Dutch used the Gregorian or New Style (NS) calendar. England still used the Julian or Old Style (OS) calendar, thus English dates were ten days earlier than Dutch dates.

¹¹ See the engraving by John Harris, "The Torments inflicted by the Dutch on the English in Amboyna" and "The Condition of the English in the Dungeon, and their Execution". c.1700, Wikimedia Commons, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Amboyna.jpg>

¹² Paulus van Wtewael, Plan of *Kampen*, 1598, Rijksmuseum, <https://www.rijksmuseum.nl/en/collection/object/Plattegrond-van-Kampen--89fff8ed248fa660565273e7bdef0879>

¹³ <https://www.british-history.ac.uk/premium-content>

The earliest reference to the wreck:

A fleet of Dutch East Indiamen had been driven into the four Needles, and two of them are wrecked. They have in them chests of silver, and other things of value, which may possibly be recovered. Advertises him thereof, that he may take care of the rights of the King and the Lord Admiral. Had sent Capt. Towerson to examine the state of the wreck¹⁴.

This emphasises the financial value of the wreck, possibly benefiting Charles I and Lord Admiral the Duke of Buckingham. The investigative role of Captain William Towerson, Portsmouth alderman, East India Company (EIC) merchant, deputy vice-admiral is identified (Moseley and Sgroi, 2010), but not that he was a cousin of Gabriel Towerson, chief EIC factor, who had been tortured and publicly executed by the VOC Governor in Amboyna in 1623 (Alsop, 2004). There is later evidence of Jacob Johnson diving and recovering coins, guns, anchors and lead ingots, which were ordered to be returned to the VOC (Larn, 1985a, 5-9).

A visit to Kampen Stedelijk Museum demonstrated the rich collection of coins minted in Kampen. Silver leeuwendaalders (lion dollars) signified the new Dutch Republic from 1579. Arendsrijksdaalders (large high value silver thalers produced by the Republic) depicted the Kampen coat of arms (Figure 24). Silver stuivers were commonly used lower value coins. Fragments of a silver 1-stuiver piece from Kampen, minted c.1621, was recorded by the Portable Antiquities Scheme in 2017 on the Isle of Wight¹⁵. This could be one of Jacob the diver's finds or scattered by the 'constant scouring of the seabed which has resulted in a high dispersal and erosion factor relating to artefacts.' (Larn, 1985a, 15). It demonstrates that Kampen-minted coins were dispersed during the shipwreck.

¹⁴ Calendar of State Papers Domestic, LXXXII, 397, 18 Oct 1627

¹⁵

<https://finds.org.uk/database/search/results/description/Campen/fromdate/1600/todate/1660/countyID/25469/material/22>

Figure 24 Dutch Republic's lion holding the Kampen coat of arms near Cellebroederspoort, one of Kampen's three remaining gates. A. Coats.

HMS Looe: 1705 5th Rate frigate

HER was a useful starting point. Thomson, Hattendorf, Miles and the Dictionary of Canadian Biography provided essential context for the War of Spanish Succession (1701–13), waged by William III and Queen Anne to protect the English Protestant succession, counter Louis XIV's domination of Europe and protect

global trade. Winfield described the 1694 5th rates¹⁶. TNA housed the most relevant archives for a Royal Navy ship, especially Captains' Letters, Courts Martial, Paybooks and Admiralty Miscellaneous (calendared online in ADM 106, an accessible aid to ordering documents) and digitised wills. Captains' Letters yielded rich descriptions of Captain Bridges' trial for killing his lieutenant in a duel in 1704 and Paybooks details about the crew.

Looe, a wooden 5th Rate 36-gun frigate of 2 decks, 390 tons BM, 108-foot x 29-foot, launched in Portsmouth Dockyard in 1697, escorted merchant convoys between the Thames and Newfoundland twice a year. *Looe* was ordered because the 1690 Battle of Beachy Head defeat fostered fears of French invasion, and the 1693 Smyrna convoy suffered extensive financial losses.

Captain Bridges had led such convoys since 1702 and was returning to Spithead round the Needles on 12 Dec 1705 when the wind changed direction suddenly and *Looe* was wrecked in Scratchwell/Scratchills Bay, Isle of Wight. The crew reached shore on a raft and locals hauled them up the cliffs, but eight seamen were drowned. Figure 25 richly illustrates how rodent damage can remove valuable data, as most entry dates and additional comments, which can reveal crew relationships and debts, is lost.

Archives provide rich social evidence for Admiralty patronage, naval convoys, legal investigation of manslaughter, shipboard life (crew relationships, impressment, desertion) and early 18th century duelling, which immensely enhance the online digital data (see Figures 26-28). But most documents are not digitised, so visiting is necessary. It would be extremely valuable to digitise Captains' Letters and Paybooks for their richness of diverse and human data.

Figure 25. TNA: *Looe* Paybook 'Eaten', ADM 33/232, 1702–1704. A. Coats.

¹⁶ Thomson, M. A., 1954, 'Louis XIV and the origins of the War of the Spanish Succession', *Transactions of the Royal Historical Society*, 5th ser., 4, 111-34; Hattendorf, John B., 1979, *England in the War of Spanish Succession A Study in the English View and Conduct of Grand Strategy, 1701–1713*, DPhil, University of Oxford; Miles, William R., 2014, 'Captains and Colonies: Royal Navy Service in the North Atlantic World, 1660–1739', DPhil, Memorial University St John's Newfoundland; Leake, Sir John, *Dictionary of Canadian Biography Volume II (1701-1740)*; Winfield, Rif, 2009, *British Warships in the age of sail 1603–1714*, Seaforth.

His orders the Sec: of Years of 17
 23rd Inst: I have nothing else to Add
 but that Cap: Bridges Commander of the
 Lord Kildes his Lieuten: in a Duell this
 Morning, the Duellist giving y^e Challenge,

Figure 26. Notification to the Navy Board by Plymouth Dock Resident Commissioner, William Wright, that Captain Bridges had killed his lieutenant in a duel, ADM 106/594, 27 February 1704. A. Coats.

Thomas Williamson late Carpenter of her
 Maj:ts Ship the Loo being Sworn deposed that on
 the 12th of Decemb: last abt. 8. a Clock in the
 morning the Said Ship being abt. a League
 W^t. of the Needles, the Capt. asked the Matr.
 if he would take the charge of the Ship & carry
 her in through the Needles, to which he
 reply'd that he wou'd, that the Capt. asked
 him again the same question, to which he
 answered that he would as well as any
 other Man, that then the Capt. bid him
 direct his Courses through the Needles, &
 come to an Anchor at Spithoad, at which

Figure 27. Loo court martial affidavit of Thomas Williams, carpenter, inscribed, TNA, ADM 1/5266, 8 January 1706. A. Coats.

Thomas Williamson late Carpenter of her Maj:ts Ship the Loo being Sworn deposed That on the 12th. of December last abt. 8. a Clock in the morning the Said Ship being abt. a league Wt. of the Needles, the Capt. asked the Matr. If he would take the charge of the Ship & carry her in through the Needles, to which he reply'd that he wou'd, that the Capt. asked him again the same question, to which he

answer'd that he would as well as any other Man, that the Capt. bid him direct the Course through the Needles, & come to an Anchor at Spithead...

Figure 28. Affidavit by William Flood, Purser, for Captain Bridges' trial at Saltash TNA, ADM 1/1466, 26 March 1704, Captains' Letters 'B', transcribed. A. Coats.

William Flood Gent Purser of her Majesties Ship *Looe*, informeth upon his Oath that in and during the space of two years last past whilst he hath been purser of the said Ship, Clement Clarke Gentleman hath been Lieutenant of the said Ship, and this Informant hath offered him the said Clarke, to be a person of very ill Behaviour and Moralls, and severall times to give Captain Timothy Bridges Commander of the said Shipp, most provoking Language, menacing him severall times to cut his Throate; and that he would not give him fair Play for his Life, and severall times hath challenged to fight the said Captain Bridges and severall other of the Officers of the said Ship...

HMS Incendiary: 1780 fire ship

Useful secondary sources were Lyon (1993, 99), Hepper (1994, 61) and Larn (both, 1995), also newspapers: *Hampshire Chronicle* (8, 29 January 1781) and *Reading Mercury* (29 January 1781). TNA records provided more detailed information. The digitised ADM 106 listing and Will of Captain William Augustus Merrick are accessible online. Further records found through the online catalogue had to be visited: logbooks of Captain Merrick, the lieutenant and master, and paybooks were valuable, also the prize papers of *De Juffrouw Cornelia Hermia*.

Built of wood by Mestears, Rotherhithe, River Thames, in 1778, the fireship *Incendiary* was 110'8" long with a crew of 45. The ship was stranded in 1780 near the Needles after a collision while escorting the captured Dutch *De Juffrouw Cornelia Hermia* (Master Laurens Pietersz) from Plymouth to Spithead. Master Charles Fea was piloting the vessel and steered close to the Needles Rocks. About 50 yards away, the wind died, and the current carried them onto the rocks. The rudder was knocked off and several planks driven in. To lighten

ship, masts and guns were removed. The crew, stores and provisions were saved. The master was found to have been drunk and incapable, was disgraced, and ordered to serve before the mast. The son of the Captain of *De Juffrouw Cornelia Hermia* was the ship's boy.

Queen Charlotte: 1815 troop ship

The aim was to find more information about this troop ship bringing 250 soldiers from the Mediterranean, which sunk on 11 March 1815. It 'ran on shore near the Needles Point, 11th inst. and is totally dismantled. Crew and soldiers saved.' (Larn 1997; HER, *Queen Charlotte*¹⁷).

Records of hiring *Queen Charlotte* and quarterly returns should exist, but none could be found. A range of sources were searched (Registers of hired ships, Imprests of hired ships, Letters to Transport Convoys, Schedule of Convoy Lists sent to Lloyd's, Courts Martial, Commanders-in-Chief Letters, Hired Armed Vessels muster books, Transport Board Minutes) but no *Queen Charlotte* troop ship was found. Despite a search using AI, no online evidence was found either.

SS Serrana: 1918 cargo and passenger ship

Secondary sources useful for the wreck: Lloyd's war losses (1990), United Kingdom Hydrographic Office, Larn (1995), Pritchard and McDonald (1987, 31-36), Young (1988, 78), Hocking (1990, 634) and Tennent (1990). Secondary sources for *UB-35*: Gröner et al (1991), Bendert (2000) and Rössler (1979).

Serrana was built in 1905 by J. Readhead and Sons, South Shields, constructed of steel, steam-powered, with a crew of 46, Master A G Maskell. It was armed with four guns, operated by Royal Marines Light Infantry and Royal Naval Reserve gunners.

Serrana was torpedoed ten miles west of St Catherine's Point without warning by *UB-35* on 22 January 1918 en-route from London to Barbados and the West Indies, carrying coal, general cargo, bricks, and railway components. *Serrana* reached the Needles Channel but grounded on the Needles Bridge Reef while the stern section drifted away before sinking. The bow section lies about 8m deep, with some cargo. The wreck was positively identified by the ship's bell. Lost were one of twelve passengers and four Barbados crew, these commemorated at Tower Hill and Longfleet St Mary Churchyard.

UB-35 sunk 42 ships, damaged 2, damaged and took 4 ships as prizes. It was wrecked after sinking *Serrana*, on 25 January 1918, depth charged by HMS *Leven* (all hands lost).

Anglo Saxon: 1879 Channel Island brig

Secondary sources established statistics: Lloyd's Foundation Survey Report (1867), Tomalin et al (2000), United Kingdom Hydrographic Office, Parliamentary papers (1880,106) and Larn (1995). Newspapers recorded the sinking: *The Star*, 4, 6 February 1879; *Shipping and Mercantile Gazette*, 3, 5, 7 and 8 February 1879; *Shields Daily Gazette*, 4 February 1879; *Jersey Independent* and *Daily Telegraph*, 8 February 1879; Lloyd's List 14 February 1879. TNA holds crew lists and agreements, 1868, 1869, 1876 and 1877.

¹⁷ https://www.heritagegateway.org.uk/Gateway/Results_Single.aspx?uid=f445ba0a-bfff-44d7-89b7-0148cb95a3fd&resourceID=19191

Anglo Saxon was built in 1868 by Matthew de Putron, Gategny yard, St Peter Port, Guernsey. A Channel Island wooden hulled brig, the sailing vessel was constructed of English oak, with a crew of 9. In 1879 *Anglo Saxon* was stranded on the Goose Rock sailing from Guernsey to London, carrying granite blocks. Experiencing SE by E force 8 wind conditions, it was wrecked near HMS *Assurance*, HMS *Pomone* and *Dream*, caught by a flood tide while attempting to enter the Needles Passage. Grounded at 3pm on 1/2/1879, it quickly filled with water, but the crew escaped. A local smack, *Alice*, recovered stores and rigging, but further attempts were abandoned within four days.

Enhancement value of analogue research evidenced

This small sample of analogue case studies suggests archival digitisation priorities but most significantly demonstrates the rich depth of new information and understanding which can enhance digital data. Experiences, processes, material culture, international connections to local events, data gaps, but above all, extraordinary human stories.

Publicly testing the Needles Voyager

The Needles Voyager was first tested onboard the MAT Discovery Bus at community events and refined by feedback before its online launch at the SWC and at further Discovery Bus events.

Embedded within Voyager is a feedback survey based on Unpath'd Waters' project-wide evaluation questions developed as part of Unpath'd Waters Work Package 5, with additional People and the Sea research questions. They mostly used a scale of 1 to 5 ranging from 'strongly disagree' to 'strongly agree'.

Needles Voyager was displayed from September 2023 until the end of August 2024, when 99 responses were received to the survey.

64% of survey responses were completed at the SWC (64), 23% online (23) and 12% on the Discovery Bus (12). SWC's larger number of surveys is likely due to some free open days where staff were specifically encouraging survey responses, with paper-based versions also available. However, this may also have been influenced by the setting of the Voyager within the museum environment and surrounded by physical shipwreck artefacts and stories, and the availability of a large touchscreen station to explore it (Figure 29).

Figure 29. The Needles Voyager touchscreen station in the SWC. MAT

Asked if Voyager provided something different from what they had experienced before, 82% either 'agreed' or 'strongly agreed', 14% were neutral, with four respondents either 'disagreeing' or 'strongly disagreeing'. This indicates that access to shipwreck stories in this format provided a new experience for many.

92% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed that the Needles Voyager allowed them to explore new shipwreck stories. When asked which stories they enjoyed the most, *Serrana* was most popular with six mentions, *Varvassi* had two mentions as did *Campan*. Other sites included *Irex*, *Anglo Saxon*, *Redbreast*, *LCT809*, *Kylin*, *Pomone* and *Mechanician*.

Other answers to this open-text question follow up on which story or stories they enjoyed the most included: 'All the older ones', 'all the ones off the Needles going back to 1800s'. Aircraft wrecks were popular with eight respondents mentioning them. There was also a more negative comment of 'Didn't learn anything from it' and two respondents said they needed more time to fully look at the content.

A considerable range of dates and types of wrecks were mentioned as popular, with some preference for First and Second World War wrecks. It is interesting that of those mentioned, few are the better-known Protected Wrecks of *Pomone* and *Assurance*, with *Pomone* having many attached resources. There was no obvious preference related to associated linked resources or material, but it is interesting to note that *Serrana* has a large range of resources available and is often in clear view when entering the Voyager initially.

Addressing thoughts on the different types of information available on Voyager, a tick box response for each type was available to indicate whether the type was viewed and how much they enjoyed each type. 'Wreck and site information' was most popular in terms of frequency of viewing, with 'people', 'artefacts', '3D models' and 'photos' also popular. Video, audio and articles were slightly less frequently viewed, however, the difference in numbers is relatively small. 3D models were popular with a higher percentage of respondents in this category choosing 'very much enjoyed', with photos similarly popular.

Only three respondents said they 'did not enjoy' resources; two did not enjoy any of the resources, with the other feeling neutral about wreck and site, people and artefact information. Such a small number of negative responses indicates that most viewers enjoyed the available resources. The wreck and site stories are available both through data embedded within the right-hand information panel on the Voyager and through pdf documents and reports, which appears to demonstrate there was no preference for the more visual materials.

Eleven respondents thought the Voyager was not easy to use, with nine being neutral, indicating that 20% of respondents had difficulties. Asked what would improve this, responses varied in relation to having instructions on use (they may have skipped this at start), having date and wreck name search function, being easier to use on mobile devices, and changing the size of the side panels. Several respondents indicated that it was easy to use after spending some time with it.

Asked if the 'Voyager was made for me', 7% disagreed, 33% were neutral, and 60% agreed or strongly agreed. This appears to indicate that many viewers found information or stories that resonated with them. However, improvements could be made here.

Asked if the Voyager experience made them feel uncomfortable, 84 respondents answered. Four agreed that they were uncomfortable, with all others either neutral or disagreed. When asked more about their response it appears that the question was interpreted differently, with some focusing on functional aspects, while others on emotional aspects. Responses included:

- "Easy to navigate, fast to run even when on a slow computer, 3d models were nice to look at".
- "Good to feel uncomfortable about tragedies".
- "It was comfortable as it was very easy to use whilst also being useful and informative".
- "This is just the best website I have seen in years and congratulate all involved in its design and build".
- "Just couldn't find my way round to get info".

87 respondents provided answers to whether they found parts of the Voyager distracting. 10 found parts distracting, with all others either neutral or disagreeing. Further information provided included:

- Held my attention through using images, videos, and 3D models with also lots of interesting facts.
- The different coloured spots were a little distracting, I would find different shapes easier.
- The map rotating when different items were selected.
- There is a lot of information and it can be hard to navigate.
- This survey box.

Asked if they were moved by the Needles Voyager 85 responded, 5 disagreeing (5%), with 41 neutral (41%) and agreeing or strongly agreeing (40%).

Demographics where gender was indicated, there was an almost equal male/female split.

A good spread of ages responded: 4 under 16, 6 = 16-18, 6 = 19-25, 8 = 26-35, 16 = 36-45, 14 = 46-55, 12 = 56-65, 17 = 66+. Of ethnicity responses, the vast majority were British or English (many choosing White British); one indicated European. Under employment status there were 11 students, 18 retired, 73 employed full-time, 14 employed part-time.

Voyager's contributions to People and the Sea Research Questions

Developing and deploying the Needles Voyager has shown how to increase audience engagement with wrecks through creating innovative digital access, in particular to related resources which enrich their stories.

Voyager makes maritime archaeological sites more accessible. It also interprets them more widely within their historical and geographical context by connecting underwater sites and their immediate geography, nearby coastal features, shoreside installations and wider tangible and intangible heritage.

It combines the most publicly available data on the Needles Protected Wrecks, particularly the *Pomone* and *Assurance* excavation collections, annual reports and photographs of artefacts. Adding archive links to sites takes viewers to online collections such as specialist websites, plans, surveys, historic photos and heritage databases, demonstrating the increasing availability of online resources. Some links to resources such as TNA, where ships' logs and crew lists are available but not digitised, demonstrate the potential for more future digital availability, but currently visits are required to see analogue resources (see Analogue Digital Connector below).

Voyager Survey feedback verifies what engages people with shipwrecks. While text-based wreck stories were generally popular, visual material such as photographs and 3D models generated more enthusiastic responses. Overall, positive responses to Voyager demonstrate that viewers are happy engaging fully digitally with wreck sites.

1.4.4 The Analogue-Digital Connector: Assessing Specialist Analogue Archives

One test which Unpath'd Waters wanted to conduct was the consideration of the 'gap' between existing digital collections (both those brought directly into Unpath'd Waters sample, and those encountered during the project) and known analogue collections. Anecdotal knowledge of the Unpath'd Waters research community was clear: there was much more information that related to marine heritage that lay beyond the digital barrier, but which, if it could be harnessed, could greatly enhance the potential for meeting the objectives of Towards a National Collection. It was equally obvious that there exists no metric by which to measure the breadth, depth or character of this gap. As part of our work on People and the Sea, the Analogue-Digital Connector (ADC) was conceived to try to illustrate the gap, to consider the challenges that would exist to crossing it, and to establish whether Unpath'd Waters could provide one approach to prioritising how such analogue collections might be unlocked (regardless of whether they relate to maritime heritage or any other cultural themes).

We decided to survey five targeted critical case- and information-rich maritime collections known to be important for wreck research. This small selection of collections was chosen because they evidence the

diversity and randomness of collections relevant to wrecks; and exhibited a variety of constraints affecting physical and part-digital collections.

The surveys aimed to ascertain characteristics, aims, user requirements and conditions, benefits and constraints, especially digital ones. Further objectives were to identify possible solutions to bridge digital collection gaps, big gaps for future action, actions/financial inputs required, and how different collection types could be united more effectively. The results were verified by interviews with the holders of the following five collections in 2024¹⁸.

The five collections

- University of Portsmouth Map Library. Created from the 1960s, this includes 20,000 maps, especially O.S. Hampshire and Isle of Wight 1:2500 County Series (unavailable digitally), Admiralty Charts and some Europe and world maps (200 digitised)¹⁹.

Constraints: No weekend access; the single Map Librarian has sole knowledge of the collection as the main Library Catalogue includes only 2% of the maps, and the succession plan for this knowledge is unclear. No capacity for cataloguing is expected in the current university funding situation, but the map librarian, who is approaching retirement, is establishing a priority list.

Opportunities: A highly knowledgeable and flexible curator.

- Portsmouth Royal Dockyard Historical Trust (PRDHT) Collection. This has been assembled since 1982, comprising 1000s of artefacts, especially 200+ unique handwritten Dockyard and local MoD Outstation Rates of Pay Books 'Rate Books' c.1870–1963 and Hurt Books 1930s–1980s (potentially 500,000 names). Also 1000s of photographs, negatives, slides, ships' drawings, tools. industrial and non-industrial work items²⁰.

It is constrained by historic employee data protection and the risk of handling the fragile Rate Books. Potential is limited by the time capacity of volunteers and an inappropriate environment (light, humidity, temperature). There is a small fee to acquire family records. Volunteers would welcome digitisation of the Rate Books for conservation reasons (Figure 30). Another benefit would be that that individual enquiries could be answered more quickly. However, they also recognise that seeing original entries is enthralling to visiting family members, who feel an emotional connection through seeing the writing and are often moved to tears.

¹⁸ Kevin Casey, Director Gosport Diving Museum, Vice-Chair Historical Diving Society; Chris Donnithorne, Navylist - Naval Biographical Database; Michael Huitson, Portsmouth Royal Dockyard Historical Trust Archive; Dr Ian Buxton MBE, University of Newcastle Marine Technology Special Collection; David Sherren, University of Portsmouth Map Collection Librarian.

¹⁹ <https://library.port.ac.uk/maps.html>

²⁰ <https://portsmouthdockyard.org.uk/>

Figure 30. PRDHT Rate Book 02A dating from c.1853. The books are stored in an uncontrolled climatic environment. Mick Huitson, PRDHT, 2023.

Opportunities: The potential for digital research is clearly enormous. Their research value as a unique and valuable source of dockyard employees who built and repaired naval and merchant vessels which later could become shipwrecked is immense. Emotional connections lead to rare items being donated, such as a 1970s jar of NAAFI coffee with a psychedelic cover, a biscuit tin containing an employee’s wage packets and a 1950 MoD Brasso tin.

- Gosport Diving Museum and the Historical Diving Society Collection of 9,000 items: reference library, archives, diving equipment²¹. The object records of the collection have been added to the Museums Data Service, launched in 2024²².

It is constrained by the time capacity of volunteers, storage capacity, museum building environment and data protection of divers on RN courses.

Opportunities: a current funded construction project consulting local disability groups will make the building more structurally sound and disability accessible when it reopens in July 2025, with a more constant temperature, leaks addressed, and another casemate revealed.

²¹ <https://www.divingmuseum.co.uk/>; <https://www.thehds.com/>

²² [https://museumdata.uk/object-search/?q=Diving%20Museum&collection\[\]=Diving%20Museum](https://museumdata.uk/object-search/?q=Diving%20Museum&collection[]=Diving%20Museum)

Interpretation will be upgraded with QR codes to download information. A PT Museum Manager and PT Community Engagement Officer will be funded for three years, and an apprentice for 18 months. More volunteers are being recruited and trained. Further storage facilities are being investigated. Visitor fees will be raised in line with nearby museums, and it will open more days.

- University of Newcastle Marine Technology Special Collection, assembled since 2010, holds records of British shipbuilding, marine engineering, ship repairing, shipbreaking industries and associated publications. As local libraries closed or disposed of their marine technology collections, they donated much significant and rare material. As shipyards and other marine businesses closed in the 1980s and 1990s valuable technical material was collected²³:

Constraints: Access is constrained because little material is available digitally (users can take their own images).

Opportunities: Some 20,000 records have been catalogued, including its unique shipbreaking records. Visitors have been able to access the British Shipbuilding Database of 82,000 British built ships. The collection was moved in 2024 to Newcastle University Library's Team Valley Research Reserve with a new archivist employed under Library management, giving more secure support.

- Naval Biographical Database was begun in the 1990s. Data currently connects 300,000 dates, 35,000 individuals, c.7,000 ships, sourced from TNA, BL, NMM and other archives²⁴. A specific task, such as linking associated events for named individuals to create career paths is achieved in under 30 seconds.

Constraints: Database is not accessible publicly. The project potential far exceeds the capacity of one individual to fully exploit. It would require copyright permission to go into the public domain, software and storage to be budgeted, and personnel to be trained to acquire and input further data to maintain data integrity. AI would be challenged by some captains' handwriting!

Opportunities: To provide, at a keystroke, referenced, accurate, updateable primary sourced material. It currently covers 1660-19th Century but expandable to link events for people individuals, organisations places and ships (and artefacts in the future). It connects 330,000 dates, 35,000 people, 7,000 ships and places with 210,000 events, supported by more than 30,000 primary source photographs. As input progresses, statistical information can increasingly be derived from complete rather than sample data, and research capability increases (reducing wear and tear on precious primary sources).

Evaluating researcher barriers to a National Collection

An expert researcher symposium – the Digital and Physical Maritime Collections Symposium – held at the Mary Rose Museum in 2023, evaluated ADC's surveys. Thirty participants (Figure 31) from across the heritage sector attended two presentations of wreck explorations and one which interrogated the following challenges:

- Barriers to access – what can we do and what can't we do and why?

²³ <https://archiveshub.jisc.ac.uk/search/locations/81d1460a-645f-3c83-b547-0d8ff6a9b46e>;
<https://archiveshub.jisc.ac.uk/search/archives/d13c89bd-cf95-39c3-8974-3ae0e481158f>;
<https://www.ncl.ac.uk/mediav8/engineering/files/Periodicals%20Histories%20M-compressed.pdf>

²⁴ <https://www.navylist.org/>

- When to digitise and when not to – precautionary principles.
- Prioritising – characterising collections and making choices.
- Discussions, including the comments of a deaf delegate, aimed at:
- Dissolving barriers – which to focus on and why?
- Characterisation – can we, should we, what would we propose for these kinds of collections?
- Potential – what kinds of evidence can we advance for the difference this would make?

Figure 31. Symposium photograph at the Mary Rose Museum, 1 November 2023, Alastair Miles.

Key findings of the eight focus groups

Question 1 What are the barriers to accessing non-digital (physical) collections?

Overall barriers

Professional language; how to search; archive processes; travel distance; type of access (opening hours, booking time, pencil/photograph) legal/security; confidence; time; deficient catalogues; curator unavailability.

Financial: Paywalls because archives are underfunded; some licence their royalties to 3rd parties behind a paywall to generate revenue; private ownerships' value; independent researchers have invested £000s to create products, so not Open Access; you don't know how useful a source is until you buy it; research bodies do not fund the full historical record; ownership of funded research.

The UK corporate model is more commercial than the Netherlands/US model which gives wider use and reuse of resources.

Specific barriers:

Users have an idea of what they want, but to connect collections would entail different resources to enable different types of people to pursue their own questions.

Knowledge level of the researcher

Legal barriers to security- and sensitive-classified documents.

Language (academic, English/other, archaic)

Physical (+cost) to access archives, increased by disability.

Institutional lack of understanding/valuing/publicising collections/imprecise catalogues/cataloguers therefore researchers do not know what is where (e.g. Trawling records at Trinity House Hull).

Risk in digitising and committing to specific platforms and/or formats due to the constantly changing software and conditions of use.

Technical terms with different meanings e.g. 'accounts' meaning financial accounts or reports/descriptions.

Divers' personal accounts and artefacts dispersed on death: irregular acquisition.

Restricted funding resources to acquire the full historical record (you do not know how long the search will take; there are fashions in projects).

Question 2: How do we prioritise collections? Major points

We cannot digitise everything: time/cost/carbon cost.

Digitising for preservation or access - most accessed (popular/most in demand) or the most threatened/fragile or the most educationally valuable? So it does not need handling - affects priorities/approaches - do it once, well, care for the asset.

A source becomes popular because it is digitised.

Endangered archives are a priority. Undervalued archives are vulnerable because they are undervalued.

Prioritisation is often determined by monetary or commercial value.

Not our place/role to decide the value. How can we know what the significance of the future will be? Basic level of curation is important for everything as we don't know future value.

Infrastructure/capabilities: many organisations/archives lack digital management software to realise the value/ leverage of what they have.

Digitise better – Digitise smarter – More interesting. Metadata is smarter – not just tagging; enrich metadata – descriptors – not just tags/keywords – narratives.

Value of the underlying data – the metadata (doing it smarter - use AI for transcription – human just checks) - more interesting'

Specific examples:

Some collections have a transnational reach: the German government has funded the TNA Prize Papers Project for 30 years covering captured C18 and C19 German ships because TNA does not have the financial resources but has the records.

Digitisation thought desirable: more medieval documents, WW2, Captains' Letters, Paybooks.

Using part of an archive that is commercially attractive could fund preservation of less 'popular' resources/records.

Symposium participant feedback:

Proactively think about and accommodate the future needs of diverse designated communities.

We need to flip our thinking about the sea as marginal to the 'real' stories that take place on land - the sea is and continues to be central to our social history.

New overall strategy needs to address the changes in paradigm shifts (also heritage at risk included areas affected by warfare). Cultural heritage has relevance to archives and digitisation. Many countries' national heritage is still under threat: ISIS, Ukraine, UK climate change, shipwrecks. Lots of rescue archaeology.

Unpath could develop an original digitisation priority framework.

Different collections could be characterised regardless of content, like Principles of Selection for Scheduled Monuments: it isn't what the asset is, but their shared characteristics that make them more or less significant.

Digitisation recommendations/framework should be developed and presented to AHRC by Project end. Could apply the criteria to a sample to see what comes out.

All prioritisation is ultimately informed by the funding source and what funding is/is not available.

A digital archive now is different from digital archive of the past and will be different again to the digital archive of the future – (pursuing higher resolutions, better modelling techniques, etc.) These moving targets for "best practice" make it difficult for an organisation to account for digitisation as a "core" task.

Could application of FAIR principles be used to inform prioritisation?

One key question asked was if the digital item could ever replace the physical item (leading to its disposal). Presently not in most cases (apart from potentially where the item is not unique?)

UK has the luxury of choice that is not available in other countries.

Symposium Debrief:

Unpath team: Why do we drive to analogue?

Practitioner: 'authority is going away and...young researchers are lazy and stop at obstacles and are vulnerable to what are facts and for deciding how to determine what facts are.'

Unpath team: 'the onus is back on ask[ing for] a trustworthy archive so that this can be used and to develop critical thinking but this development of critical thinking has to be experienced it cannot be imparted by us to others.'

Unpath team: 'schools are particularly interested [in 3.2] and specifically if we can talk about science with heritage case studies...and use STEM as a tool, a key to apply to maritime history in order to get them interested'.

1.4.5 Archaeology on the Seabed: Audience-Driven Narratives

Archaeology on the Seabed (AotS) developed new narratives and a more inclusive understanding of significance to engage people with shipwrecks in new ways

This demonstrated the impact of integrating diversity of interest and voice for any future national collection. The following summarises and gives examples of the results presented in a separate WP 3.1 technical report (Wessex Archaeology 2024).

HER of shipwrecks and recorded vessel losses within the territorial waters of the Solent, Isle of Wight and inshore areas formed the base dataset. Data enhancement used online sources, including Lloyd's Register Foundation archive of ship plans and records and the Crew List Index Project for crew and other records. Specialist searches were undertaken for selected themes. Volunteers from local communities and groups critically examined the existing historic record and co-created new narratives.

Themes: C18 and C19 century ship names and associated named persons, selected for possible connections with Africa or the Caribbean, were checked against the online Slave Voyages and UCL Legacies of British Slavery databases to check links with the trade and ownership of enslaved persons.

The base dataset was analysed by the researcher, a white British male with over twenty years' professional involvement in UK maritime archaeology to identify and choose themes likely to be of interest to the local communities whose help was sought: South Asian connections; Caribbean connections; African connections; Far and South East Asian connections; South Sea and Australasia connections; and Environmental damage and risk. Wreck and loss records relevant to each theme were then enhanced from online sources and from some People and the Sea sources. Co-creators recruited through internet searches and word of mouth for all the themes, except the last, were not from a White British background. For example, a volunteer from the African Women's Forum was sought in respect of the African and Caribbean connections theme through that organisation's website. Contacting and persuading people to volunteer by 'cold calling' proved much more difficult than anticipated but five co-creators were recruited. Archaeology on the Seabed was designed before Unpath target groups were selected, and the study could not align with these.

Each volunteer selected wrecks or losses from a theme that interested them, and commented on the enhanced assessment of each vessel, to identify what was engaging and significant to them and the groups or communities with which they identified. This occurred through an online person-to-person discussion between the co-creator and the researcher, who subsequently sent a summary of the notes to the co-creator for approval.

Results

Although a small study, it has demonstrated considerable scope to enhance our knowledge of shared maritime archaeology and its significance by working with new and diverse voices.

Co-creator 3 was British South Asian with a Bangladeshi Muslim background. A member of the British South Asian group, Chat over Chai, which has previously worked with NMRN and UoP, she declared a prior interest in maritime heritage.

She selected the South Asian connections theme and HMS *Sphinx*, lost in 1846. The Research Record identified that *Sphinx* was built in Bombay Dockyard. Record enhancement discovered that it was built by members of the South Asian Parsi Wadia family and a contemporary portrait of one shipbuilder exists in the online collections of the Royal Asiatic Society of Great Britain and Ireland ([RAS 01.007-01.008] Jamsetjee

Bomanjee (1756-1821) and Nourojee Jamsetjee (1774-1860), shipbuilders - Royal Asiatic Society Online Collections (royalasiaticcollections.org)).

The co-creator selected *Sphinx* because her grandmother was Parsi, giving an immediate family connection. Chat over Chai has also helped NMRN understand the significance of another Wadia ship built in Mumbai (then Bombay), HMS *Trincomalee*. The contribution that Indian shipbuilders made to the Royal Navy, about 30 ships, is important to the group. For the co-creator the ship's importance lies in the local link with this story that the loss provides. *Sphinx* is also likely to have been built at least partly of teak and she felt that the stripping of teak forests in India to build Royal Navy and British and Indian merchant ships is a shared experience with environmental overtones that deserves better recognition. She noted that the building of ships for the Royal Navy by Indian shipbuilders could also be seen as a mark of quality and, to some extent, respect.

Co-creator 2, similarly from a British South Asian background and with a prior interest, also selected this wreck because of a family connection. She hails from a Mumbai neighbourhood with a Parsi connection, and her father worked for a Parsi business. She therefore had an emotional connection with *Sphinx*. She had been unaware of the Parsi shipbuilding connection before her involvement, but knew of the benefits the community had obtained from cultivating business relationships with the British during the Raj. She saw the *Sphinx* as a symbol of their rise and of an era of trade between Britain and India of which British Indians know little. She emphasised that the Wadia family are now industrialists with a large textile business and that the famous Tata family is Parsi. *Sphinx* also spoke to her about how the British treated Indians as separate communities, a so-called 'divide and rule' policy. She also felt that it was important to develop narratives linking maritime and terrestrial monuments, something that the study did not attempt. Both Co-creators felt that the stories of the South Indian crew aboard some of the ships was a narrative not yet fully recognised and a little known but important part of the significance of the wrecks to their communities. Both recognised the lack of records helpful to family research in India and therefore the origin and fate of these men.

These results are only samples, but they provide evidence that ethnicity and national identity are important drivers of interest in maritime heritage in sections of the UK public. When first recruited, it was striking that Co-creator 1 of the African Women's Forum, a woman with a strong connection to her home city Portsmouth, was also very clear that her interest in maritime heritage lay solely in its ability to provide black role models for young people in the city. Overall, she felt that the current national record did not pay sufficient attention to the associations between the ships concerned and Black people. The same concern with people came through differently through the comments about *Sphinx* of Co-creators 2 and 3. Personal as well as community and ethnicity connections are clearly important. For those interested in the 'who' rather than the 'what', the existence of 'paywalls' requiring fees to gain access to information about people onboard is frustrating.

Co-creators who engaged with the Environmental damage and risks theme, all White British, were recruited through environmental lobby groups and were clearly interested in understanding historic wrecks in terms of their impact upon the environment. Co-creator 5, a committed environmental campaigner, expressed interest in drawing parallels between historic wrecks and the contemporary environmental campaigns that she is involved through Greenpeace and Friends of the Earth but felt that the existing national heritage records did not provide enough information to determine which wrecks might be of interest.

Archaeology on the Seabed's strong audience-led link with Unpath's Discovery Objectives ensures its relevance to People and the Sea. It has provided insight, albeit small, into the diversity of interest and theme that any future national collection aiming to be fully representative of society will require, and benefit from.

1.4.6 Case Study Outcomes

A significant number of public engagement outcomes were achieved by People and the Sea. Mary Rose Museum and UoP Immersive Co-Creation Subgroup garnered very positive visitor feedback about new animations to attract and retain visitors and correct misconceptions about *Mary Rose*. With UoP IC-CS, NAS created a Hollands Explorer Prototype Immersive using new photogrammetry combining *Holland 1* and *5* which has attracted very encouraging feedback from adults and schoolchildren. MAT's new Needles Voyager Immersive, displayed in the Discovery Bus over the last two years, has collected favourable feedback from hundreds of visitors online and on paper. The ADC process corrected some of *Campen's* data on the MAT Needles Voyager. CITiZAN collaborated with MAT and WP5 in devising participant values and updated its citizen-led dataset on the intertidal zone where volunteers have identified more than 2,000 new features and added 6,000 images to the Unpath'd Waters portal. WA obtained people-focused data about physically inaccessible wrecks through diverse community perspectives which adds a further dimension to the design of a national collection.

Improving the reliability of wreck data, NAS refined Holland submarine information and will benefit from improved Holland accessibility through the NMRN website. Utilising MAT's archive, UoP Analogue Digital Connector discovered fascinating new archival stories about four Needles wrecks, to be added to the Voyager.

Analogue Digital Connector also researched maritime collections' constraints and challenges and consulted a symposium of heritage experts to advise on digital policies to achieve a virtual national collection.

1.4.7 New Engagements, New Forms of Significance

The answer to the key research questions:

1. How can we establish what engages different people with historic wrecks either onshore in museums or offshore still submerged, and what does that mean for the way we as nations protect and provide access to them?
2. How can we enhance the significance of submerged and displayed wrecks and thus increase audience engagement and prioritise management decisions?

Q1

The different case studies developed by the People and the Sea team provide convincing and nuanced evidence of what engages people with wrecks.

New information – the capacity for discovery of something entirely unknown. But also that this capacity is constrained by the limited current digitisation of analogue resources, AI capacity and user expertise.

Enhanced information – bringing collections together digitally provides increased exploratory routes. Connectivity such as Voyager makes maritime archaeological sites more accessible. It also interprets them more widely within their historical and geographical context by connecting underwater sites and their immediate geography, nearby coastal features, shoreside installations and wider tangible and intangible

heritage and material culture. Such enhanced information highlights the international and multicultural nature of ships and shipwrecks.

Combined media – the power of word, audio, image, video and 3D modelling and representations reaches different kinds of people in different ways.

Listening to feedback – enables adapting the mechanisms for combining collections to suit multiple audiences.

Challenging people to find their own solutions – Voyager offers varied pathways to vessels, aircraft, terrestrial sites or processes; hackathons bring together multidisciplinary teams to create new discovery routes.

Reflecting on people-centred stories – it is less about the wrecks and more about the people whose lives revolved around or were touched by the wrecks. This is a key point throughout *People and the Sea*, but especially from the work around diversity themes.

Provoking by proposing new narratives – the ability for combined collections to trigger new ways of thinking.

The non-heritage value of heritage – heritage as inspiration, environmental lobbying, social wellbeing.

Q2

The PWA73 Act states “on account of the historical, archaeological or artistic importance of the vessel”.

Combining collections provides a challenge and opportunity to think about what kinds of importance might influence the selection of a candidate for protection.

The lessons from wrecks in museums is the complexity of the relationships between observer/experiencer and the totality of the wreck. Physicality is one thing (for instance, the scale of *Mary Rose*) but also its temporal trajectory (conceived, built, launched, travelled, lost, found, recovered, conserved, displayed, experienced) and the people and things associated with it (stories, artefacts) are clearly another vital set of engagements.

We can show that undertaking this with wrecks below the water works, perhaps not as well, but certainly to a much greater extent than is currently possible, using the array of digital resources.

It is important to note that those selecting favourites in the *Needles Voyager* case study did not pick the most well-known and well-publicised of the wrecks – *Pomone* and *Assurance*. Instead, they picked out other stories. Participants in *Archaeology on the Seabed* also selected vessels with personal resonations. This suggests that engagement is self-driven not ‘marketing’-driven and that the enhanced choices through connected collections permitted these choices.

The conclusions are that *People and the Sea* has brought Protected Wrecks and their stories, alongside other known wrecks, into far greater focus for a much greater audience. But a more accessible national collection needs more investment in selected digitisation and user guides and exploration of how paywalls hinder public access to collections.

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